

Fig. S7. Phylogenetic signal across sample of 100 trees for each Myrmarachnini (A. and B.) and Castianeirinae (C. and D.). A. and C. Pagel's lambda; B. and D. Blomberg's K. Note that estimates for some traits in Castianeirinae must be handled with caution due to insular trait expression: 'Lateral cephalothorax constriction' (Lat cephaloth. const.), 'Dorsal cephalothorax constriction' (Dors. cephaloth. const.), 'Lateral abdomen constriction' (Lat. abdom. constr.), 'Dorsal abdomen constriction' (Dors. abdom. constr.), 'Illusion by colouration'. The high abundance of non-expression returns a very high or very low phylogenetic signal for those traits.